

A Synthetic Interferometric ISAR Technique for Developing 3-D Signatures

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Abstract—This paper presents a technique for directly obtaining 3-Dimensional (3-D) Radio Frequency (RF) signatures. The technique allows 3-D signatures to be generated from 2-Dimensional (2-D) Inverse Synthetic Aperture Radar (ISAR) signatures. At the present time, there is a problem with obtaining height information from non-monopulse radar systems. Since many of the radar test ranges only have non-monopulse radar systems, implementation of this concept would have great benefits as the cost to upgrade the current systems to fully polarimetric monopulse capabilities is significant.

band to validate the concept. This paper presents the findings of the test, most notably problems encountered in this conceptually elegant and readily implemented technique and methods to overcome these difficulties. Simulations of a proposed method to enhance the performance of SIFISAR for signature determination indicate that the SIFISAR concept is viable under suitable conditions.

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2. TEST DESCRIPTION—TEST ONE

Initial testing of the SIFISAR concept was conducted 14-15 November, 2001. During the 14-15 November testing, two frequency bands were utilized in the test, X-Band (10-11 GHz) and Ka-Band (35-36 GHz) and three depression angles (2, 30, and 60 degrees). The radar used in the test was the Millimeter-wave Instrumentation High Resolution Imaging Radar System (MIHRIRS). The radar employed 128 frequency steps of 8 MHz each at both X and Ka-Bands. A complete set of coherent polarimetric data was recorded for each run (HH, HV, VV, VH).

1. INTRODUCTION

Detailed target signatures can be obtained by making Inverse Synthetic Aperture Radar (ISAR) measurements. Down range and cross range resolutions are functions of radar bandwidth and view angle respectively. Obtaining scatter height with non-monopulse systems however, is a problem. Unfortunately, many important test ranges do not have monopulse radar systems. Upgrading these systems to a fully polarimetric monopulse capability entails significant cost. This report presents findings for a technique denoted as Synthetic Interferometric ISAR (SIFISAR) that is being investigated for use by non-monopulse instrumentation radar systems to obtain scatter height in ISAR images. The basic concept is to generate 2 images; through 2 data collection passes, of the target with the radar at a slightly different height for the second pass. The difference in radar height between the passes 1 and 2 generates the interferometric baseline. An interferogram is developed from $Image1 \times Image2^*$ where Image1 is the complex image obtained from pass 1 and Image2* is the complex conjugant of the complex image obtained in pass 2. The resulting phase of the interferogram can then be used (theoretically) to obtain relative height of the scatters in the scene. Tests of the concept were conducted at X and Ka-

Three target arrays were used in the test. The first, denoted as Array #1, was a single 10.5-inch trihedral reflector placed on a tripod. The tripod height was 4 feet with the legs being covered with milliken rug RAM. The tripod was 62" to the right of table center and was in the center of the table with respect to down range. A reference reflector was placed on the ground 20 feet back from turntable center, 17 feet to the left of the turntable center as shown in Figure 2.1. The setup is shown in Figure 2.2. The reference was a 12-in. trihedral placed on a RAM covered tripod 50 inches off of the ground.

Array configuration #2 consisted of three 10.5" trihedral reflectors placed on tripods on top of the turntable. The tripod legs were covered with milliken rug RAM. In relation to 0° the tripods were set-up as follows: Tripod #1 remained in place from Array #1, and was 4' in height and 62" from center of turntable on right side. Tripod #2 was 24" height and 74" towards the tower from center and 82" to the left. Tripod #3 was 70" in height and 4' by 4' left rear from the center of the turntable. Array #1 was a single 10.5" trihedral reflector placed on a tripod on top of the turntable. The tripod legs were covered with milliken rug RAM. The tripod height was 4' and it was 62" from center of turntable on right side. The reference reflector was the same as in Array configuration #1.

Fig. 2.1. Array #1 Configuration, the Table is shown rotated -45 degrees for the start of a run.

Fig. 2.2. ISAR Image.

Array configuration #3 consisted of a single post-placed 62" from turntable center with two 10.5" trihedral reflectors placed vertically. The bottom trihedral was placed at 13" in height with the top trihedral 49" above. The post was wrapped with milliken rug RAM and black anechoic RAM was placed between the trihedral and around post base. The reference reflector was the same as in array configurations 1 and 2.

Data were collected over a ± 45 -degree arc at nominally 0.016-degree increments. After the first pass of a test configuration was made the turntable was reset and the radar height raised 1.0 m and the test repeated. No changes were made to the target array or reference reflector between passes 1 and 2. For the 2-degree depression case a third pass was made with the antenna raised 0.2 meters from the position of pass 1. This was done to allow investigation of interferometric baseline on the SIFISAR technique. Figure 2.2 contains an ISAR image formed from one of the data sets.

3. HEIGHT EXTRACTION USING TWO-PASS IFISAR

The procedure used to extract the height of the scatters from the ISAR images is shown in block diagram from in Figure 3.1. This procedure is based on a technique used in IFISAR [1]. Additional information on IFISAR can be found

in the open literature [2-5]. The first step is to read in the desired segment of data from each of the two passes. A pre-processing program was written to perform this function. The center segment of the data set (~ 0 deg) was used in the analysis presented in this report. The second step is to focus the data from Pass 2. Figure 3.2 helps to explain this step. Ideally the antenna would be a constant distance from scene center from the two passes, this would allow the scatters to be in the same range bins in the resulting ISAR images. However, since the antenna was raised straight up the tower for Pass 2, the distance to scene center is greater in Pass 2 than in Pass 1. A phase correction can be made to the data set for Pass 2 based on the difference in path length (δl) using the following expression

$$\phi_{focus} = \frac{4\pi \cdot \delta l}{\lambda_{1,n}} \quad (3.1)$$

The phase correction is applied to each High Range Resolution (HRR) waveform, which in this experiment consisted of 128 pulses. After the focusing is performed the scatters will line up along range bins in the two resulting ISAR images. The next step is to center both data sets, if necessary, so that scene center (middle of the turntable) is in the center of the image; this is done by applying a phase shift to both data sets.

Fig. 3.1. SIFISAR Height Calculation Procedure.

Fig. 3.2 Tower Configuration.

The next step is to compress each data set in range and cross range by taking the two-dimensional inverse Fourier transform of the data sets. The result is a set of complex two-dimensional functions, the magnitude of which is a standard ISAR image of the scene. The next step is denoted as fine phase compensation. The fine phase compensation is performed to remove errors caused by frequency drift of the radar between the two passes and any motion of the tower between the two passes. The fine phase compensation term is found by comparing the phases of the reference reflector in complex image 1, denoted as P_1 with the phase of the reference reflector in complex image 2, denoted as P_2 . The next step in the process is to form an interferogram by

$$IGram = P_1 \cdot P_2^* \quad (3.2)$$

where P_2^* is the complex conjugate of P_2 . The phase of the interferogram is denoted as $\delta\phi$ and can be used to find the height of the scatters in the image. Figure 3.2 defines the angle θ . The relationship between $\delta\phi$ and θ is given by

$$\theta = -\sin^{-1}\left(\frac{-\delta\phi \cdot \lambda_c}{4\pi \cdot B}\right) \quad (3.3)$$

where λ_c is the wavelength at the center of the HRR waveform and B is the interferometric baseline. The height of the scatters in the scene are given by

$$H \cong R \cdot \tan(\theta) \quad (3.4)$$

The SIFISAR procedure of Figure 3.1 was tested on a set of simulated data as a verification step. The test array consists of three Gaussian shaped reflectors on a flat surface. The scatters and the RCS of the scatters are shown in Figures 3.3(a) and 3.3(b) respectively.

4. ANALYSIS OF SIFISAR TECHNIQUE— TEST ONE

The initial data sets (one and two) represent two passes at a depression angle of 2° with an X-Band waveform. The interferometric baseline (difference in antenna heights between passes 1 and 2) is 0.2008 meters. The same procedure used to process the simulated data in Section 3 was used to calculate scatter heights from these two passes. Figure 4.1 contains the phase of the resulting interferogram and Figure 4.2 contains the magnitude of the interferogram. Figure 4.1(a) contains the raw or unfiltered phase and Figure 4.1(b) contains the smoothed (2-D low pass filtered) phase. The phase appears to be a random variable. Figure 4.3 contains the height estimate obtained from the smooth interferogram phase of Figure 4.1(b). It is clear that Figure 4.3 does not accurately represent the heights of the reflectors used in the test. Additional data sets were analyzed with similar results; the interferogram phase is essentially random.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3.3. (a) Height of Test Array; (b) RCS of Test Array.

Fig. 4.1. Phase of the Interferogram for D
(a) Unfiltered, (b) Smoothed

Fig. 4.2. Normalized Magnitude of the Interferogram
for Data Sets One and Two.

Fig. 4.3 Scatter Heights Derived from Interferogram
for Data Sets One and Two.

Consideration of the test setup explains the resulting interferograms obtained from this test. The tabletop is covered in RAM, so ideally there should be no return from any cells other than the ones containing on the corner reflectors. The RAM is not a perfect absorber so some small return is received. However, the returns from the RAM only cells after ISAR image formation must compete with receiver noise. It is postulated that the returns in the RAM only cells are essentially noise. This means that the phase of the ISAR images from the two passes are uncorrelated except for where there are corner reflectors. Unfortunately, these random phase variations result in height errors that are unacceptable.

5. TEST DESCRIPTION—TEST TWO

On 12 July 2002, further testing was completed to investigate techniques to overcome some of the problems encountered in the earlier SIFISAR test. Specifically, the experiment was designed to determine the effect of having a continuous target as opposed to the point targets (trihedrals) used in the original test back in November, and to test the effects of having a scattering surface, instead of RAM on top of the turn table. Analysis of the November 2001 results indicated difficulties in obtaining the height of isolated-discrete point scatters using the SIFISAR technique. This led to the hypothesis that a target of some extent should be used and that a portion of the "target" should consist of a flat, rough surface that can be used as a reference point for scatter heights.

A simple test was conceived to check the extended target hypothesis. Limited resources available for the test dictated the sophistication of the phenomenology array. It was decided to use a piece of corrugated metallic sheet with stones at its base as the reference surface.

The phenomenally fence used in the test is depicted in Figure 5.1. The fence consists of two 2' x 8' sheets of

corrugated metallic roofing material. The sheet was canted at 45° and was placed in the center of the turntable. Stones were placed in front and to the sides of the sheet after the RAM on the tabletop was removed to serve as the reference plain. The stones are standard landscaping material and were approximately 1 to 4 inches in length. Stones were chosen over sand and sod since extensive testing of these materials at AMCOM revealed that their RCS is too small for this test [6]. However, it was simply an assumption on the author's part that the stones would provide a larger and sufficient RCS to support this experiment.

The radar used in the test was the Millimeter-wave Instrumentation High Resolution Imaging Radar System (MIHRIRS). The radar employed 128 frequency steps of 8 MHz each at X-Band (10–11 GHz). Due to instrumentation problems, only VV polarization data was collected during the test. The data format for the files obtained from MIHRIRS is given in Appendix A. The radar was operated with a single receiver and with two receivers. The two receiver configuration was utilized to collect data for single pass interferometric ISAR imaging.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5.1. Photograph of the Phenomenology Array.

6. CONCLUSIONS—TEST TWO

Once again the procedure explained in section 3 was used to extract the height of the scatters from the ISAR images. Two passes were made, once again obtaining two data sets. The initial analysis looked at a broadside aspect angle (0 degrees on the turntable), 128 azimuth points were utilized and these are plotted in Figure 6.1. The ISAR images were over $\sim 2^\circ$ as shown in Figure 6.1. The spacing between azimuth angles is nominally 0.015° . Ideally, the turntable would be at the same azimuth orientation for the two passes, however, as expected there is some error. Figure 6.2 is a graph of the difference between the table positions on a sample-by-sample basis. As can be seen from Figure 6.2, the table position differs by at most 0.009° between the two runs. It is believed that this difference can be ignored. Figure 6.3 and 6.4 are the resulting images when the 128 azimuth cuts are range compressed for pass one and two respectively. These plots are of interest in determining if the fence and reference reflector show up in all 128-azimuth cuts.

Fig. 6.1 Turntable Position for Data Set One.

Fig. 6.2. Difference in Turntable Position for Data Sets One and Two.

Fig. 6.3. Range Compressed Image for Pass One.

Fig. 6.4. Range Compressed Image for Pass Two.

The next step in the process, as outlined in Figure 3.1, is to do the fine phase compensation for each azimuth sample (HRR profile). After phase compensation the phase of the reference reflector is 0° in each of the range compressed HRR profiles in both data sets. There is an issue with this approach that warrants consideration: since the radar is moved for the second pass resulting in a different path length to the reference, the phase of the reference reflector should not in general be 0° . If the precise position (to within $\pm\lambda/8$) of the reference reflector where known, the phase of the reference reflector in the second pass could be set accordingly. However, this is not the case, the position of the reference reflector was measured with a tape measure and therefore is only approximately known. The issue of the phase of the reference reflector in the second pass is an area requiring further consideration as the SIFISAR technique matures.

The resulting interferogram for the data sets is shown in Figure 6.5. Figure 6.5(a) contains the magnitude of the interferogram and Figure 6.5(b) contains the phase of the interferogram. A pattern can be discerned in the phase plot, which is encouraging. Earlier work using only corner reflectors produced only a noise like interferogram phase. Figure 6.6 is a plot of the angle θ from equation 3.3, which

is used to find scatter height by way of equation 3.4. Only the values of θ for the area containing the "Target" are of interest, the values of θ over the RAM covered tabletop are essentially a random variable and do not provide any useful information. To precisely determine where the target is located the center azimuth cut (column 64) of the interferogram magnitude is shown in Figure 6.7. The reference reflector occupies cell 44 as expected and the target area occupies cells 59-64. The center azimuth cut for θ is shown in Figure 6.8. The calculated scatter heights for the center azimuth cut is shown in Figure 6.9(a) with a blow up of the region of interest (elements 59-64) shown in Figure 6.9(b). The height of the radar fence is 0.863 m; the height given in Figure 6.9(b) is 0.38 m. The ideal values of θ and the corresponding scatter heights are shown in Figures 6.10(a)-(b) respectively. The target area occupies azimuth cuts 62-66. A review of scatter heights for these azimuth cuts shows no correlation with Figure 6.9. It is concluded that while Figure 6.9 is at first glance encouraging, it does not represent an accurate portrayal of the radar fence.

Fig. 6.5. Interferogram for Data Sets One and Two
(a) Magnitude (b) Phase.

Fig. 6.6 Resulting Calculation of θ .

Fig. 6.7. Center Azimuth Cut of the Interferogram.

Fig. 6.8. Center Azimuth Cut of θ .

Fig. 6.9. Resulting Scatter Height, Center Azimuth Cut.

Fig. 6.10. The Ideal (a) Angle θ and (b) Scatter heights for the Radar Fence.

7. SUMMARY

The results from this second test of the SIFISAR concept are encouraging, a distinct pattern was observed in the phase of the interferogram, however, accurate scatter height was not produced. Lessons learned from the test include: increasing the size of the reference plane (rocks), increasing the grazing angle of the radar, and utilizing a target that is not as directional. The limited size of the reference plane in this test was an artifact of resources available at the time of the test. Also, it appears that a steeper grazing angle is desirable, it is postulated that the RAM on the tabletop was partially obscuring the rocks. The corrugated metallic sheet was chosen as a target due to limited preparation time available for the test. It is desirable in future tests to have a target that is not as directional as the metal sheet. Arrangements are currently being made to obtain a data set from the National Ground Intelligence Center, taken in an indoor range, for use in further development of the SIFISAR technique.

8. REFERENCES

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BIOGRAPHIES

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